

Human Resource Management Practices and the Digital Revolution of FINTECH Companies in Nigeria

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The study assessed the nexus between Human Resource Management Practices (dimensioned by performance management and diversity and inclusion) and the digital revolution (measured by technological adoption and financial inclusion) of FINTECH companies in Nigeria. The research was underpinned by the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology and guided by the positivism philosophy. The research design adopted a cross-sectional survey approach, and a structured questionnaire based on a Likert's five-point scale. The target population was 30 FINTECH companies registered in Nigeria, with head offices in Lagos State, and the elements of the accessible population were 150 middle and top-level managers of the registered FINTECH firms. The Taro Yemene's formula was utilised to determine a sample size of 109 respondents, and the snowball sampling was adopted. Partial least squares-structural equation modeling was deployed to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significance level. The study revealed a significant and positive relationship between Diversity and Inclusion practices and Financial Inclusion within Nigerian FINTECH firms, highlighting the critical role of inclusive organizational cultures in enhancing accessibility to financial services. However, the findings also indicate a lack of significant relationships between Performance Management and both Technological Adoption and Financial Inclusion, as well as between Diversity and Inclusion and Technological Adoption. Therefore it is recommended that Managers of FINTECH firms should continue to invest in and strengthen their diversity and inclusion initiatives. This can help to create a more inclusive environment that supports broader financial access and service provision, by providing equal opportunities for career advancement to all employees, regardless of background.

Key words: Human resource management practices, digital revolution, FINTECH companies

INTRODUCTION

The transition towards a "digital economy" with estimated worth of \$11.5 trillion globally, has been phenomenal and the digital revolution has profoundly transformed Fintech companies in Nigeria, enhancing financial inclusion, operational efficiency, and economic growth. In Nigeria, the Financial Technology (FINTECH) companies have evolved to emerge as one of the top ecosystems in Africa, where three of the five FinTech unicorns in Africa are Nigerian companies: Interswitch, Flutterwave, and OPay. In 2020, U.S. payments giant - Stripe paid over \$200 million to acquire Paystack, while Tiger Global valued Flutterwave at over \$1 billion. Moreso, the fintech

companies in Nigeria engaged in a broad range of product offerings spanning payment solutions, investment and online banking, and they are looking to expand the tentacles of the financial sector to reach its unbanked population of 60 million people (Knewtson & Rosenbaum, 2020; Kola-Oyeneyin et al., 2020). However, Fintech companies in Nigeria face numerous challenges such as regulatory uncertainty and cumbersome licensing requirements (Adebayo, 2020; Olagunju & Ajayi, 2018). Additionally, infrastructural issues such as poor internet connectivity and unreliable power supply disrupt fintech services, particularly in rural areas, thereby increasing operational costs (Ezeoha, 2019; Oseni & Pollitt, 2013). Moreso, economic challenges, including difficulty in securing investment and the instability of the Nigerian economy, further constrain the scalability of fintech

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startups (Ibrahim & Muritala, 2020; Akanbi, 2021). On the other hand, digital financial services have expanded access to financial products, particularly for unbanked populations in rural areas, thus fostering economic participation and poverty reduction (Akinola, 2019; Evans & Pirchio, 2015).

In view of the foregoing, this study measured digital revolution by technological adoption and financial inclusion, where technological innovation refers to the process of developing new technologies or improving existing ones to enhance productivity, efficiency, and competitive advantage in various sectors, while financial inclusion involves providing individuals and businesses with access to affordable, timely, and adequate financial services, including savings, payments, credit, and insurance, that meet their needs. It aims to ensure that all people, especially those in underserved and marginalized communities, have the opportunity to participate fully in the financial system (Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2018). Moreso, this study adopted human resource management practices as a predictor of digital revolution, where human resource management (HRM) practices refer to the strategic approach organizations adopt to effectively manage their workforce and enhance their performance. Two critical dimensions of HRM practices are performance management and diversity and inclusion. Performance management involves the continuous process of setting goals, monitoring employee progress, providing feedback, and evaluating overall performance to ensure that organizational objectives are met. It helps in identifying areas of improvement, rewarding high performance, and fostering employee development (Armstrong, 2017). On the other hand, diversity and inclusion refer to HRM practices that promote the representation and participation of individuals from varied backgrounds, including gender, ethnicity, age, and cultural differences, within the workforce. These practices create an inclusive environment where all employees feel valued, respected, and able to contribute to their full potential (Olsen & Martins, 2012). Effective diversity and inclusion initiatives enhance creativity, problem-solving, and innovation within organizations by leveraging a wide range of perspectives and experiences. Therefore, this study assessed how human resource management practices (dimensioned by performance management and diversity and inclusion) relates with digital revolution (measures by technological adoption and financial inclusion) of FINTECH Companies in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The problem of this study is poor level of adoption of digital revolution by Fintech companies in Nigeria. Poor adoption of the digital revolution by Fintech companies in Nigeria manifests in several detrimental ways, impacting both the companies and the broader economy. Limited

financial inclusion remains a significant issue, as many Nigerians continue to rely on cash transactions due to the inadequate reach of digital financial services, hindering full economic participation and access to essential financial services (Eze, 2019; Awolaye, 2018).

Additionally, fintech companies that fail to embrace digital technologies experience operational inefficiencies, leading to higher costs, slower service delivery, and reduced competitiveness (Oladejo, 2020). Likewise, inadequate consumer trust is another critical problem, as insufficient digital adoption prevents fintech firms from implementing strong security measures, leading to consumer skepticism about the safety of digital transactions (Udo, 2021). The poor level of adoption of the digital revolution by fintech companies can be attributed to several factors such as: Lack of technological infrastructure (Akingbade & Sola, 2021), high implementation costs (Oladimeji & Adeola, 2020). Additionally, the skills gap in emerging technologies such as data analytics and cybersecurity presents a challenge, as many firms struggle to find and retain talent capable of driving digital transformation (Nwafor & Onyekachi, 2019). The effects of poor adoption of digital technologies in fintech companies include: Inability to keep up with the rapid pace of innovation in the financial services sector (Oladimeji & Adeola, 2020), inefficiencies in operations persist, cybersecurity vulnerabilities, and missed growth opportunities. To address the problem poor adoption of the digital revolution by fintech companies in Nigeria, several solutions have been suggested, including creating a more supportive regulatory environment through clear guidelines and regulatory sandboxes (Adewale, 2019; Omotayo, 2020), investing in infrastructure, particularly improving internet connectivity and ensuring reliable power supply in rural areas (Okeke, 2021; Ogunleye, 2018), raising financial literacy levels through awareness campaigns, educational programs, and integrating financial education into school curricula (Adebisi, 2020; Olawale, 2019), building consumer trust by prioritizing data security, transparent communication about security practices, and offering prompt customer support to alleviate consumer concerns and improve the user experience (Udo, 2021; Nwafor, 2020). However, despite the avalanche of plausible solutions, the problem of poor adoption of the digital revolution by fintech companies in Nigeria, still persists. This suggests a contextual gap in literature. Therefore, this study sought to close the gap by critically examining human resource management practices (dimensioned by performance management and diversity and inclusion) and how it relates with the digital revolution (measured by technological adoption and financial inclusion) of fintech companies in Nigeria. The study aims to achieve the following specific objectives:

i. Assess the link between performance management and technological adoption of FinTech companies in Nigeria.

- ii. Investigate the relationship between performance management and financial inclusion of FinTech companies in Nigeria.
- iii. Determine the nexus between diversity and inclusion and technological adoption of FinTech companies in Nigeria.
- iv. Assess the relationship between diversity and inclusion and financial inclusion of FinTech companies in Nigeria.

The research questions are as follows:

- i. How does performance management relates with technological adoption of FinTech companies in Nigeria.
- ii. What is the relationship between performance management and financial inclusion of FinTech companies in Nigeria.
- iii. How does diversity and inclusion relates with technological adoption of FinTech companies in Nigeria.
- iv. What is the relationship between diversity and inclusion and financial inclusion of FinTech companies in Nigeria.

The formulated null hypotheses are:

HO1: There is no significant link between performance management and technological adoption of FinTech companies in Nigeria.

HO2: There is no significant relationship between performance management and financial inclusion of FinTech companies in Nigeria.

HO3: There is no significant link between diversity and inclusion and technological adoption of FinTech companies in Nigeria.

HO4: There is no significant relationship between diversity and inclusion and financial inclusion of FinTech companies in Nigeria.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Human Resource Management Practices and dimensions (Armstrong, 2020). Digital Revolution and Measures (Odiase, 2018).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital Revolution of FinTechs: The digital revolution of fintech companies refers to the transformative shift from traditional financial services to technology-driven solutions that enhance efficiency, accessibility, and customer experience. This revolution involves the integration of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence, blockchain, and mobile applications into financial services, enabling faster and more secure transactions, personalized financial products, and greater financial inclusion (Gomber et al., 2017).

Technological Adoption: Technological adoption refers to the process by which an individual or organization integrates a new technology into their routine practices (McManis, 2023). It encompasses not just acquiring the technology, but also understanding its functionalities, developing skills to use it effectively, and ultimately, incorporating it into workflows to achieve desired outcomes (Noe, Tams, & Jung, 2020). This process is often multi-faceted, involving factors like user needs, perceived benefits, ease of use, and organizational support (Rogers, 2003).

Financial Inclusion: Financial inclusion refers to the ability of individuals and businesses to access a wide range of affordable financial products and services to manage their financial well-being (World Bank, 2023). This encompasses essential services like savings accounts, credit, money transfers, and insurance. Financial inclusion is crucial for reducing poverty and promoting economic development, as it empowers individuals and businesses to participate more fully in the financial system (Demirguc-Kunt & Klapper, 2017).

Human Resource Management Practices: Human resource management (HRM) practices encompass the various activities and processes an organization employs to attract, develop, motivate, and retain a high-performing workforce (Noe, Tams, & Jung, 2020). These practices cover a broad spectrum, including: recruitment and selection, training and development, performance management, compensation and benefits as well as employee relations.

Performance Management: Performance management is a systematic process within organizations focused on setting clear expectations, providing ongoing feedback, and developing strategies to improve individual and team performance (Noe, Tams, & Jung, 2020). It involves establishing measurable goals aligned with organizational objectives, regularly evaluating employee performance against those goals, and offering constructive feedback to help employees bridge any gaps. This cyclical process fosters continuous improvement, motivates employees, and ultimately contributes to achieving organizational goals (Bratton & Gold, 2020).

Diversity and Inclusion: Diversity and Inclusion represent a multifaceted approach to fostering a work environment that reflects and respects a wide range of

backgrounds, identities, and experiences (American Psychological Association, 2021). Diversity encompasses the variety of social identities present within a group, including race, ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, age, ability, and religion. Inclusion goes beyond simply having a diverse workforce; it focuses on creating a culture where everyone feels valued, respected, and empowered to contribute their unique skills and perspectives (Society for Human Resource Management, 2023).

Theoretical Framework: The theory that underpinned the study is the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) (Venkatesh et al., 2003). The proponents of the UTAUT argue that the effectiveness of certain factors, such as anticipated benefits, perceived effort, social influence, and conducive surroundings, are all crucial in determining the intention and utilisation of information systems (Venkatesh et al., 2003). The present study finds the UTAUT relevant as the theory offers a valuable framework for understanding how the adoption and acceptance of necessary technology can enhance human resource management practices, ultimately leading to improved digital revolution (proxied by technological adoption and financial inclusion) of FinTech companies in Nigeria.

Empirical Reviews: Khalfan, et al. (2022) examined the relationship between technology adoption and the performance of business organisations involved in manufacturing. This study was conducted quantitatively, with data collected via questionnaire survey. The collected data was used to develop the model of structural relationship between the factors using PLS-SEM approach. The study was found that performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating condition all have a positive relationship with technology adoption. Moreso, Shathees et al. (2020) investigated the relationship between technology adoption drivers and employee job performance in the Malaysian Manufacturing Industry. Employing a quantitative research method, data was collected from 370 respondents through a structured online survey questionnaire. The findings indicated that job satisfaction and motivation to be statistically significant while the workload was failed to be retained in the research. Likewise, Ghosh, (2022) analysed the relevance of linguistic diversity on financial inclusion in India. The findings show that linguistic polarization leads to a significant decline in bank account ownership and its use. Similarly, Akingbade and Sola (2021) examined the impact of human resource management practices, specifically performance management, on the digital transformation of fintech companies in Lagos, Nigeria. Using a survey research design, they collected data through questionnaires distributed to 150 HR managers and IT personnel across 10 fintech companies. The analysis, conducted with Structural Equation Modelling (SEM), revealed a strong positive relationship between performance management practices and the successful

adoption of technological tools in fintech firms. Also, Oladimeji and Adeola (2020) explored the relationship between diversity and inclusion policies and the adoption of financial technology in Nigerian fintech startups. Employing a mixed-methods approach, they combined qualitative interviews with quantitative analysis of survey data from 200 fintech employees. Their findings indicated that fintech firms with robust diversity and inclusion practices experienced faster and broader adoption of digital financial services. The study highlighted that employees from diverse backgrounds contributed to innovative solutions, leading to more inclusive financial products and increased customer engagement. Futherstill, Nwafor and Onyekachi (2019) investigated the role of human resource management practices, with a focus on both performance management and diversity, in enhancing financial inclusion through digital solutions in Nigerian fintech companies. The study used a cross-sectional research design and collected data from 250 employees across fintech companies in Nigeria. Using Partial Least Squares - Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM), the analysis revealed that performance management and diversity initiatives had significant positive impacts on financial inclusion strategies within fintech firms.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted a cross-sectional survey approach, and a structured questionnaire based on a Likert's five-point scale. The target population was 30 FINTECH companies registered in Nigeria, with head offices in Lagos State, and the elements of the accessible population were 150 middle and top-level managers of the registered FINTECH firms. The Taro Yemene's formular was utilised to determine a sample size of 109 respondents, and the snowball sampling was adopted. Partial least squares-structural equation modeling was deployed to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significance level. 80 copies of the instrument (74.40%) were retrieved and found to be adequately completed and usable. A minimum Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.7 was adopted as reliability cut-off point for this study, while an average variance extracted (AVE) of 0.5 and above indicated sufficient convergent validity. Moreover, the discriminant validity is confirmed when the square root of a construct's AVE is greater than its correlation with all other constructs (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Figure 2, and table 1 reveals the reflective measurement model of human resource management practices (dimensioned by performance management and diversity and inclusion) and how it relates with digital revolution (measured by technological adoption and financial inclusion) of FinTech Companies in Nigeria, with the following interpretation: All items except DANDI1, FININC1 and 4 have indicator reliability (λ^2) above 0.50.

Figure 2: Measurement (Outer) Model
 Source: SmartPLS 4.1.0.0 Research Data, 2024

Also, PERFM6, DAND16 and TECHAD5 were deleted because they loaded below 0.5. The composite reliability and Cronbach’s Alpha values exceeded the threshold of 0.7. The AVE’s exceeded the minimum threshold of 0.5,

indicating adequate convergent validity. Moreso, the square roots of all the constructs were higher than the construct correlations, showing evidence of discriminant validity.

Table 1: Result for Reflective Measurement Models

Constructs	Items	Convergent Validity			Internal Consistency Reliability			
		Path coefficient (β)	Indicator Reliability (I_k^2)	AVE	Composite Reliability (ρ_c)	Effect sizes (f^2)	Predictive Accuracy (R^2)	Cronbach's Alpha (α)
Performance Management	Our organization provides clear expectations for my performance	0.793	0.629	0.566	0.862	0.377	0.274	0.789
	In Our firm, we receive regular and constructive feedback on our level of performance.	0.856	0.733					
	In our company, performance evaluations are fair and unbiased.	0.760	0.578					
	In our company, outstanding performance is recognized and rewarded appropriately.	0.884	0.781					
	Our organization provides opportunities for me to improve my performance.	0.820	0.672					
	Our performance objectives are aligned with the organization's strategic goals.	Deleted	deleted					
DIVERSITY AND INCLUSION	Our organization's culture promotes inclusiveness for all employees.	0.689	0.475	0.538	0.868	52.499	0.981	0.808
	Our organization has a diverse representation of employees at all levels.	0.827	0.684					
	Our organization provides equal opportunities for career advancement to all employees, regardless of background.	0.821	0.674					
	Our firm offers effective training programs on diversity and inclusion.	0.833	0.694					
	Employees in our organization respect and value differences in backgrounds, perspectives, and experiences.	0.771	0.594					
	Our organization actively supports and advocates for underrepresented or marginalized groups.	deleted	deleted					
TECHNOLOGICAL ADOPTION	Our organization frequently adopts new technologies to enhance its operations.	0.860	0.740	0.612	0.887	1.712	0.631	0.821
	The organization invests significantly in research and development for technological advancements	0.896	0.803					
	Our organization provides adequate training for employees on emerging technologies.	0.834	0.696					
	Digital tools and platforms are effectively implemented and utilized within our organization.	0.874	0.764					
	Our organization encourages and supports innovative ideas and solutions from employees.	deleted	deleted					
	Technological innovations have significantly improved the efficiency and productivity of our organization.	0.820	0.672					

Table 1:Contd.

FINANCIAL INCLUSION	Our organization provides easy access to digital financial services for all users.	0.637	0.406	0.558	0.882	1.065	0.516	0.858
	Digital financial services offered by our organization are affordable for a wide range of users.	0.719	0.517					
	In our firm, the digital financial platforms provided are user-friendly and easy to navigate.	0.861	0.741					
	Our organization offers programs to improve financial literacy and understanding of digital financial services.	0.610	0.372					
	Our organization ensures the security and privacy of users' digital financial transactions.	0.844	0.712					
	The digital financial services provided by our organization are inclusive and cater to underserved communities.	0.775	0.601					

Source: SmartPLS4.1.0.0 Output of Research Data, 2024

Figure 4: Structural Model showing the beta values and p-values
Source: SmartPLS 4.1.0.0 Research Data, 2024

Figure 5: Structural Model showing the beta values and t-values.

Source: SmartPLS 4.1.0.0 Research Data, 2024

Table 2: Results of Hypotheses Testing

Null Hypo.	Stages	Path Coefficients (β)	R^2	T Statistics ($t \geq 1.96$)	P Values ($p < 0.05$)	Decision on Null Hypotheses
H ₀₁	PERFM→TECHAD	0.046 (Weak)	0.642 Moderate	0.687 (Not Significant)	0.492 (Not Significant)	Supported
H ₀₂	PERFM→FININC	0.025 (Weak)	0.591 Moderate	0.370 (Not Significant)	0.711 (Not Significant)	Supported
H ₀₃	DANDI→TECHAD	0.106 (Weak)	0.921 Strong	1.176 (Not Significant)	0.240 (Not Significant)	Supported
H ₀₄	DANDI→FININC	0.358 (Weak)	0.591 Moderate	3.724 (Significant)	0.000 (Significant)	Not Supported

Source: SmartPLS 4.1.0.0 Output of Research Data, 2024

DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

Relationship between Performance Management and Technological Adoption: From figures 3 and 4, and table 2, the results from testing the hypothesis H₀₁ indicate that there is no significant link between performance management and technological adoption. The path

coefficient (β value) of 0.046 suggests a weak positive relationship, but with a p-value of 0.492 and a t-value of 0.687, the relationship is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

Additionally, the R^2 value of 0.642 indicates a moderate level of predictive accuracy, meaning that while the overall model explains a moderate proportion of the

variance in technological adoption, performance management itself is not a key driver. These findings imply that performance management practices have minimal impact on technological adoption in Nigerian FINTECH companies, suggesting that other factors or HRM practices might play a more significant role. Surprisingly, this particular finding disagrees with Khalfan, et al. (2022) who found that performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating condition all have a positive relationship with technology adoption.

Relationship between Performance Management and Financial Inclusion: From figures 3 and 4, and table 2, the results from testing the hypothesis H02, reveal that there a weak positive but no significant link between performance management and financial inclusion. The path coefficient (β value) of 0.025 indicates a very weak positive relationship, and with a p-value of 0.711 and t-value of 0.370, this relationship is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level. The moderate R^2 value of 0.591 suggests that while the overall model explains a moderate proportion of the variability in financial inclusion, performance management itself does not emerge as a significant driver. These results imply that changes in performance management practices have minimal impact on financial inclusion within Nigerian FINTECH firms. Interestingly, this finding agrees with Ghosh, (2022) who found that that linguistic polarization leads to a significant decline in bank account ownership and its use.

Relationship between Diversity and Inclusion and Technological Adoption: From figures 3 and 4, and table 2, the results from testing the hypothesis H03, indicate that Diversity and Inclusion do not exhibit a significant link with Technological Adoption. The path coefficient (β value) of 0.106 suggests a weak positive relationship, while the p-value of 0.240 and t-value of 1.176 indicate that this relationship is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level. Despite the substantial R^2 value of 0.921, which signifies a high level of explanatory power in the overall model for Technological Adoption, Diversity and Inclusion alone do not significantly contribute to explaining the variance in this context. These results imply that while Diversity and Inclusion practices may be important for organizational culture and employee engagement, they may not directly influence the adoption of new technologies within Nigerian FINTECH firms. However, this finding disagrees with Shathees et al. (2020) who found that there was no statistical evidence for the mediating effect of job insecurity in the research.

Relationship between Diversity and Inclusion and Financial Inclusion: From figures 3 and 4, and table 2, the results from testing the hypothesis H04, reveals a significant positive relationship between Diversity and Inclusion and Financial Inclusion. The path coefficient (β value) of 0.358 indicates a moderate correlation, with a p-value of 0.000 and t-value of 3.724, confirming statistical

significance at the 0.05 level. This implies that Diversity and Inclusion practices play a meaningful role in enhancing Financial Inclusion within Nigerian FINTECH firms. The moderate R^2 value of 0.591 suggests that Diversity and Inclusion, among other factors, explain a substantial portion of the variability in Financial Inclusion outcomes. These findings underscore the importance for organizations to prioritize and strengthen Diversity and Inclusion initiatives as integral components of their strategies to improve financial services accessibility and inclusivity. This finding agrees with Khalfan, et al. (2022) who found that performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating condition all have a positive relationship with technology adoption.

CONCLUSION

The study revealed a significant and positive relationship between Diversity and Inclusion practices and Financial Inclusion within Nigerian FINTECH firms, highlighting the critical role of inclusive organizational cultures in enhancing accessibility to financial services. However, the findings also indicate a lack of significant relationships between Performance Management and both Technological Adoption and Financial Inclusion, as well as between Diversity and Inclusion and Technological Adoption. These results underscore the nuanced impact of HRM practices on digital revolution outcomes in the FINTECH sector. Moving forward, organizations should prioritize enhancing Diversity and Inclusion initiatives while reevaluating and potentially refining their Performance Management strategies to better align with digital transformation goals.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1). Enhance Diversity and Inclusion Initiatives: Managers of FINTECH firms should continue to invest in and strengthen their diversity and inclusion initiatives. This can help to create a more inclusive environment that supports broader financial access and service provision, by providing equal opportunities for career advancement to all employees, regardless of background.
- 2). Reassess Performance Management Strategies: Managers of FINTECH firms should revisit their performance management strategies to ensure alignment with broader organizational goals, including technological adoption and financial inclusivity. This may involve incorporating metrics and incentives that encourage innovation and digital transformation.
- 3). Integrate Findings into Strategic Planning: Management of FINTECH firms should incorporate the study findings into strategic planning processes to optimize HRM practices and digital strategies. This could involve adjusting resource allocation, training programs,

and policies to better support both diversity goals and digital transformation efforts.

Suggestions for Further Research

Further research could conduct qualitative research methods could uncover underlying mechanisms and organizational barriers affecting these relationships, offering richer contextual understanding.

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